

A curated set of mating-type assignment for the blast fungus (Magnaporthales)

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ABSTRACT

Conflicting mating type annotations are frequent in *Magnaporthe* (Syn. *Pyricularia*) *oryzae* literature. Here, we classify the mating types of 14 standard strains and 258 genome samples of *Magnaporthe* sp. based on the protein structure-based nomenclature of Turgeon & Yoder (2000). We hope that our dataset will help to reduce confusion about mating type nomenclature in Magnaporthales and will facilitate comparisons across studies.

MAIN TEXT

The ascomycete fungus *Magnaporthe* (Syn. *Pyricularia*) *oryzae*, the causal agent of blast disease of cereals, requires two compatible partners for mating to occur (heterothallism) (Ni et al. 2011). Thus, sexual reproduction can only take place between individuals of two opposite mating types (Dean et al. 2005; Zhang, Zheng, and Zhang 2016; Wang et al. 2021). The mating-type alleles were originally identified using a combination of genomic subtraction and restriction fragment length polymorphisms (RFLP) (Kang, Chumley, and Valent 1994). As in other Ascomycetes (Staben and Yanofsky 1990; Debuchy and Coppin 1992; Turgeon et al. 1993), the isolated genes contained non-homologous sequences (idiomorphs) instead of classical alleles, and were named MAT1-1 and MAT1-2 after the *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* MAT1 locus. The original mating type naming did not take into account the different protein features encoded in the MAT1-1 and MAT1-2 idiomorphs due to historic technological constraints and the lack of a standardised notation system.

To establish a common nomenclature, Turgeon and Yoder (Turgeon and Yoder 2000) proposed a standard system based on conserved Ascomycete-wide protein domains and motifs exclusive to each of the idiomorphs. The first idiomorph MAT1-1 contains the alpha box motif, first described in the MAT α 1 protein of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, while the second idiomorph MAT1-2

contains a DNA-binding domain of the high mobility group (HMG) type. In spite of this unambiguous protein structure-based classification system, there is a lack of consistency in the literature. Several studies have assigned the mating type based on the original mating-type label assigned to commonly used fertility tester isolates, hence, conflicting mating type annotations have been propagated until present days. This conflict can create misleading interpretations about mating-type diversity when comparing different studies. In *M. oryzae*, the problem is well illustrated by Table 1 in Kanamori *et al*, 2007 (Kanamori et al. 2007).

Here, we classify mating types for a wide number of *Magnaporthe* sp. isolates based on the protein structure-based nomenclature (Turgeon and Yoder 2000). For this purpose, we used proteins carrying the alpha box motif and the HMG group to diagnose MAT1-1 (MAT1-1-1; GenBank: BAC65091.1) and MAT1-2 (MAT1-2-1; GenBank: BAC65094.1), respectively, for a collection of 258 publicly available genome sequences. We conducted *TBLASTN* searches using the NCBI nucleotide collection (nr/nt) and the NCBI whole-genome shotgun contigs as databases, restricting the results to the order Magnaporthales and retaining results, with both query coverage and percentage identity superior to 90%.

We provide a protein structure-based classification for commonly used *Magnaporthe* sp. isolates present in the NCBI nucleotide collection (Table 1). As an example that illustrates conflicts in mating type assignments in the literature, isolates KA3 and TH3 which have been known as standard testers for MAT1-1 (Shen et al. 2004; D'Ávila, De Filippi, and Café-Filho 2019), do not carry the alpha box within the MAT1 locus but the HMG group instead. Conversely, the isolate GUY11, known as a tester standard for MAT1-2 (Leung 1988; Nottéghem, Silue, and Others 1992; Kang, Chumley, and Valent 1994; Saleh et al. 2012), carries the alpha box motif within the MAT1 locus. Hence, the isolate GUY11 should be labelled as MAT1-1 and isolate TH3 as MAT1-2 based on Turgeon and Yoder (Turgeon and Yoder 2000) classification. Additionally, we provide protein structure based classification for 258 *Magnaporthe* sp. genomes present in the NCBI whole-genome shotgun contigs database (Supplementary Table 1).

Table 1. Structure-based mating-type assessment in different *Magnaporthe* sp. isolates.

Isolate	Alpha box / HMG	Structure-based MAT1 classification	GenBank
70-6	Alpha box	MAT1-1	AB080670.2
70-14	HMG	MAT1-2	AB080671.2
70-15	HMG	MAT1-2	AACU03000155.1
B71	HMG	MAT1-2	LXOQ01000178.1
GUY11	Alpha box	MAT1-1	MQOR01001043.1
HB1	Alpha box	MAT1-1	MF993977.1
Hoku-1	Alpha box	MAT1-1	AB080668.2
LpKY97	Alpha box	MAT1-1	CP050926.1
MZ5-1-6	Alpha box	MAT1-1	CP034210.1
P2	HMG	MAT1-2	AB080669.2
SD1	HMG	MAT1-2	MF993976.1
TH3	HMG	MAT1-2	CAJHMK010009395.1
Y93-164a-1	HMG	MAT1-2	AB080673.2
Y93-164g-1	Alpha box	MAT1-1	AB080672.2

CONCLUSION

We hope that our dataset will help to reduce confusion about mating type naming in Magnaporthales and will facilitate comparisons across studies. We agree with the approach of Turgeon and Yoder (Turgeon and Yoder 2000). We recommend the implementation of the protein structure-based mating type classification, because it is consistent with the majority of the ascomycete literature, and it permits unambiguous assignment of mating types to isolates for which genome sequences are the only available data. Publicly available sequences can be used as diagnostic references: MAT1-1 (MAT1-1-1; GenBank: BAC65091.1) and MAT1-2 (MAT1-2-1; GenBank: BAC65094.1).

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Supplementary Table 1. Structure-based mating-type assessment in whole-genome shotgun databases of *Magnaporthe* sp. isolates.

Isolate	Alpha box / HMG	Structure-based MAT1 classification	GenBank	Isolate	Alpha box / HMG	Structure-based MAT1 classification	GenBank
401.4	HMG	MAT1-2	JMJY01002343.1	IE1K	Alpha box	MAT1-1	PJYG01000104.1
903.4	HMG	MAT1-2	JMJX01001557.1	IT10	HMG	MAT1-2	JMRE01004234.1
1106.2	Alpha box	MAT1-1	JMKE01001613.1	JL10	HMG	MAT1-2	JMJQ01001753.1
1801.4	HMG	MAT1-2	JMKD01005442.1	JS-10-6-1-2	HMG	MAT1-2	MQPM01001270.1
1836.3	HMG	MAT1-2	JMKC01005139.1	JS08-611	HMG	MAT1-2	MQPN01001452.1
2303.1	Alpha box	MAT1-1	JMKB01005412.1	JS09-138	HMG	MAT1-2	MQPO01001636.1
2539	HMG	MAT1-2	VCMT01000276.1	JS25	HMG	MAT1-2	JMJP01001843.1
4403.2	HMG	MAT1-2	JMKA01004428.1	JX-09Z116-1	HMG	MAT1-2	MQPP01000394.1
4603.4	HMG	MAT1-2	JMJZ01002127.1	JX10-102	HMG	MAT1-2	MQPQ01000466.1
10100	Alpha box	MAT1-1	PYAN01000140.1	JX11-141	HMG	MAT1-2	MQPR01000434.1
4091-5-8	Alpha box	MAT1-1	AOCH01003881.1	K84-01	HMG	MAT1-2	JMQS01002493.1
13FM-16-1	Alpha box	MAT1-1	MQNR01001333.1	K88-07	Alpha box	MAT1-1	JMQT01002957.1
13FM-24-1	Alpha box	MAT1-1	MQNS01000095.1	K88-24	HMG	MAT1-2	JMQU01000850.1
13FM-3-2	HMG	MAT1-2	MQNT01001489.1	K91-10	HMG	MAT1-2	JMQV01000137.1
13FM-5-1	Alpha box	MAT1-1	MQNU01001176.1	K91-13	HMG	MAT1-2	JMQW01001259.1
13FM-9-1	HMG	MAT1-2	MQNV01001334.1	K91-30	Alpha box	MAT1-1	JMQX01005340.1
70-14	HMG	MAT1-2	AB080671.2	K93-16	HMG	MAT1-2	JMQY01004493.1
70-15	HMG	MAT1-2	AACU03000155.1	K96-07	Alpha box	MAT1-1	JMQZ01004281.1
70-6	Alpha box	MAT1-1	AB080670.2	K96-11	HMG	MAT1-2	JMRA01002467.1
87-120	Alpha box	MAT1-1	PQBK01001379.1	K98-02	HMG	MAT1-2	JMRB01002090.1
98-06	HMG	MAT1-2	JRBC01000190.1	K98-10	Alpha box	MAT1-1	JMRC01001954.1
AG002	HMG	MAT1-2	CAJHIG020000014.1	KA1-3-1	Alpha box	MAT1-1	MQPS01001413.1
AG006	HMG	MAT1-2	CAJHIH020000013.1	KA2-1-1	Alpha box	MAT1-1	MQPT01000195.1
AG032	HMG	MAT1-2	CAJHID020000014.1	KJ201	HMG	MAT1-2	ANSL02002408.1
AG038	HMG	MAT1-2	CAJHIC020000009.1	Lc8401	HMG	MAT1-2	JABCQT010000070.1
AG039	HMG	MAT1-2	CAJHII020000004.1	Lh88405	Alpha box	MAT1-1	JAALIM010000054.1
AG059	HMG	MAT1-2	CAJHIF020000017.1	LpKY97	Alpha box	MAT1-1	CP050926.1
AG098	HMG	MAT1-2	CAJHIE020000013.1	MG01	HMG	MAT1-2	AYPX01001963.1
AH06	HMG	MAT1-2	JMJW01000574.1	MG02	HMG	MAT1-2	LNTH01007854.1
Arcadia	Alpha box	MAT1-1	PJZD01000066.1	MG03	HMG	MAT1-2	LNTJ01009342.1
Arcadia2	Alpha box	MAT1-1	JAALIO010000011.1	MG05	HMG	MAT1-2	LNTI01007541.1
AV1-1-1	Alpha box	MAT1-1	MQNW020000011.1	MG07	HMG	MAT1-2	LNTL01013433.1
B157	HMG	MAT1-2	AXDJ01002252.1	MG08	Alpha box	MAT1-1	LNTN01008694.1

B2	Alpha box	MAT1-1	PJZC01000408.1	MG10	Alpha box	MAT1-1	LNTM01007560.1
B51	Alpha box	MAT1-1	PJZB01000126.1	MG12	Alpha box	MAT1-1	LNT001008014.1
B71	HMG	MAT1-2	LXOQ01000178.1	ML33	Alpha box	MAT1-1	PJYE01000151.1
Bd8401	Alpha box	MAT1-1	PJZA01000082.1	Mo-nwi-31	Alpha box	MAT1-1	JGVY01000256.1
BdBar16-1	HMG	MAT1-2	LXON01001325.1	Mo-nwi-55	HMG	MAT1-2	AZSW01004174.1
BdJes16-1	HMG	MAT1-2	LXOO01000211.1	MZ5-1-6	Alpha box	MAT1-1	CP034210.1
BdKUS	HMG	MAT1-2	JAALDJ010000146.1	N06047	HMG	MAT1-2	CAJVN010000052.1
BdMAG	HMG	MAT1-2	JAALDI010000149.1	NI907	Alpha box	MAT1-1	RRCK01000005.1
BdMeh16-1	HMG	MAT1-2	LXOP01000176.1	Nich-2-3-2	Alpha box	MAT1-1	MQPU01000284.1
BJ-90-611	HMG	MAT1-2	MQNX01001200.1	Nich-2-7-4	Alpha box	MAT1-1	MQPV01000339.1
BJ08-8	HMG	MAT1-2	MQNY01000839.1	NX37	HMG	MAT1-2	JMJO01006576.1
BM1-24	Alpha box	MAT1-1	JMRG01005433.1	P-0028	Alpha box	MAT1-1	MKZV01000028.1
Bm88324	Alpha box	MAT1-1	PJYZ01000001.1	P-0029	HMG	MAT1-2	MLCC01000259.1
Br116	Alpha box	MAT1-1	JAALDH010000371.1	P131	HMG	MAT1-2	AHZT01001264.1
Br118	HMG	MAT1-2	JAALDG010000377.1	P2	HMG	MAT1-2	AB080669.2
Br130	HMG	MAT1-2	PJYW01001986.1	P28	Alpha box	MAT1-1	PJYD01000002.1
BR32	HMG	MAT1-2	UEMB03000005.1	P29	HMG	MAT1-2	PJYC01000162.1
Br35	Alpha box	MAT1-1	JAALDF010000201.1	P3	Alpha box	MAT1-1	PJYB01000136.1
Br62	Alpha box	MAT1-1	JAAKGW010000661.1	Pd88413	Alpha box	MAT1-1	JAALDD010000371.1
Br7	Alpha box	MAT1-1	PJYY01000392.1	pg1213-2	Alpha box	MAT1-1	JABCQP010000296.1
Br80	HMG	MAT1-2	PJYX01000194.1	Pg1213-22	HMG	MAT1-2	PJYA01000176.1
Br81	HMG	MAT1-2	JAALDE010000610.1	PH42	Alpha box	MAT1-1	PJXZ01000082.1
BTGP1-b	HMG	MAT1-2	UCOG02000042.1	PL2-1	Alpha box	MAT1-1	PJXY01000001.1
BTGP6-f	HMG	MAT1-2	UCOF02000006.1	PL3-1	HMG	MAT1-2	PJXX01000176.1
BTJP4-1	HMG	MAT1-2	UCOD02000035.1	PMg_DI	HMG	MAT1-2	RHLM01000011.1
BTMP13-1	HMG	MAT1-2	UELY02000005.1	Po237	HMG	MAT1-2	JAAKHA010003766.1
CA205	HMG	MAT1-2	JMRH01003632.1	PR003	HMG	MAT1-2	CAJHIJ020000009.1
CD156	HMG	MAT1-2	UELZ03000006.1	PR01-37.V.1.05	HMG	MAT1-2	JAAXMU010000938.1
Cd88215	Alpha box	MAT1-1	JAALIN010000005.1	PR01-37.V.3.07	HMG	MAT1-2	JAAXMV010001025.1
CHRF	Alpha box	MAT1-1	PJYV01000208.1	PR72	HMG	MAT1-2	JMRF01004297.1

CHW	Alpha box	MAT1-1	PJYU01000041.1	Pr8202	Alpha box	MAT1-1	JABCQS010000115. 1
CQ11	HMG	MAT1-2	JMJV01004084.1	Py22.1	HMG	MAT1-2	MILZ01000225.1
DB11-621	HMG	MAT1-2	MQNZ01001099.1	Py5020	HMG	MAT1-2	MKIG01000408.1
DS0505	Alpha box	MAT1-1	LOEM01000735.1	RMg-DI	HMG	MAT1-2	MBSD03000003.1
DS9461	Alpha box	MAT1-1	LOFB01001376.1	San_andrea	HMG	MAT1-2	CAJHIK020000017. 1
DsLIZ	HMG	MAT1-2	PJYT01000009.1	Sar-2-20-1	Alpha box	MAT1-1	MQPW02000001.1
EI9411	HMG	MAT1-2	LOFC01000030.1	Sar-AD3-5	Alpha box	MAT1-1	MQPX01001684.1
EI9604	Alpha box	MAT1-1	LOFD01000882.1	SC-10-120-65-2	Alpha box	MAT1-1	MQPY01001655.1
EtKY19-1	HMG	MAT1-2	JAAGOI010006138.1	SC-10-25-44-1	Alpha box	MAT1-1	MQPZ01001402.1
FH	Alpha box	MAT1-1	PJYS01000476.1	SC05	HMG	MAT1-2	JMJN01002515.1
FJ0204804	Alpha box	MAT1-1	MQQA01000911.1	SD1	HMG	MAT1-2	MF993976.1
FJ11SH-527-1	Alpha box	MAT1-1	MQQB01000087.1	SSFL02-1	HMG	MAT1-2	PJXW01000012.1
FJ11YD-673-1	Alpha box	MAT1-1	MQQC01000539.1	SSFL14-3	HMG	MAT1-2	PJXV01000024.1
FJ12JN-084-3	Alpha box	MAT1-1	MQOD01000553.1	SSTX16-11	HMG	MAT1-2	JAALDC010000009. 1
FJ13SH05-2	Alpha box	MAT1-1	MQOE01001057.1	SV9610	Alpha box	MAT1-1	LOFE01000147.1
FJ2000-62A	Alpha box	MAT1-1	MQOF01000458.1	SV9623	HMG	MAT1-2	LOFF01000234.1
FJ2000-69A	Alpha box	MAT1-1	MQOG01001376.1	T25	HMG	MAT1-2	PJXU01000223.1
FJ2001-112B	Alpha box	MAT1-1	MQOH01001510.1	TF05-1	Alpha box	MAT1-1	PJXT01000057.1
FJ2003-001A1	Alpha box	MAT1-1	MQOI01001532.1	TF15-1	Alpha box	MAT1-1	JAALCZ010000174. 1
FJ2005113B	Alpha box	MAT1-1	MQOJ01001377.1	TH3	HMG	MAT1-2	CAJHMK010009395 .1
FJ2006-60A3	Alpha box	MAT1-1	MQOK01000528.1	TP2	Alpha box	MAT1-1	JAAKGX010000187. 1
FJ43ZB15-68	HMG	MAT1-2	MQOL01000274.1	TW-1-1-1-B-1	HMG	MAT1-2	MQQA01001181.1
FJ72ZC7-77	Alpha box	MAT1-1	MQOM02000006.1	TW-12CY-TB1-2	HMG	MAT1-2	MQQB01001589.1
FJ78-JJ	HMG	MAT1-2	MQON01000092.1	TW-12HL-DF1-2	HMG	MAT1-2	MQQC01001318.1
FJ81-JY	HMG	MAT1-2	MQOS01000091.1	TW-12HL-YL2-1	HMG	MAT1-2	MQQD01000116.1
FJ81-MH	HMG	MAT1-2	MQOT01001499.1	TW-12TD-RH1-1	HMG	MAT1-2	MQQE01000185.1
FJ81-SW	HMG	MAT1-2	MQOU01000631.1	TW-12TN-HB2-2	HMG	MAT1-2	MQQF01001105.1
FJ81-ZP	HMG	MAT1-2	MQOV01000424.1	TW-12YL-DL3-2	HMG	MAT1-2	MQQG01000460.1
FJ81221ZB11-14	HMG	MAT1-2	MQOW01000006.1	TW-12YL-DP1-1	HMG	MAT1-2	MQQH01000794.1
FJ81278	HMG	MAT1-2	MQOQ01001071.1	TW-12YL-TT4-1	HMG	MAT1-2	MQQI01000633.1
FJ86-CT	HMG	MAT1-2	MQOX01000516.1	TW-2-7-2-A-1	HMG	MAT1-2	MQQJ01000117.1
FJ86061ZE3-39	HMG	MAT1-2	MQOY01001450.1	TW-6-2-2-B-1	HMG	MAT1-2	MQQK01001089.1
FJ95054B	HMG	MAT1-2	MQOZ01001088.1	TW-6-43-1	HMG	MAT1-2	MQQL01000561.1

FJ95085AZB13-11 6	Alpha box	MAT1-1	MQPA01000074.1	TW-CYBP1-3	HMG	MAT1-2	MQQM01001235.1
FJ98099	Alpha box	MAT1-1	MQPB02000009.1	TW-PT1-1	HMG	MAT1-2	MQQN01001751.1
FJ99138	Alpha box	MAT1-1	MQPC01000926.1	TW-PT3-1	HMG	MAT1-2	MQQO01001454.1
FJSH0703	Alpha box	MAT1-1	MQPD01000076.1	TW-PT6-1	HMG	MAT1-2	MQQP01001204.1
FPH-2015-44	HMG	MAT1-2	JAALDB010000031. 1	TW-TN4-2	HMG	MAT1-2	MQQQ01001758.1
FR13	HMG	MAT1-2	UEMA03000006.1	U168	HMG	MAT1-2	JABCQR010000017 .1
G17	Alpha box	MAT1-1	PJYQ01000298.1	US71	Alpha box	MAT1-1	UCNY03000007.1
G22	HMG	MAT1-2	PJYP01000098.1	V86010	Alpha box	MAT1-1	MWIT01000229.1
GD-05-029b	Alpha box	MAT1-1	MQPE01001194.1	VO107	HMG	MAT1-2	PJXS01001697.1
GD06-53	Alpha box	MAT1-1	MQPF01000099.1	W97-11	HMG	MAT1-2	ANKU01001202.1
GD08-2025	Alpha box	MAT1-1	MQPG01001784.1	W98-20	Alpha box	MAT1-1	ANOW01001740.1
GD22	HMG	MAT1-2	JMJU01002509.1	WBKY11	HMG	MAT1-2	PJXR01000006.1
GG11	Alpha box	MAT1-1	PJYO01000002.1	WBSS	HMG	MAT1-2	PJXQ01004786.1
GOV41	HMG	MAT1-2	JMRD01002619.1	WD-3-1_1	Alpha box	MAT1-1	MQQR01001681.1
GrF52	Alpha box	MAT1-1	PJYN01000165.1	WHTQ	HMG	MAT1-2	PJXP01003639.1
GUY11	Alpha box	MAT1-1	MQOR01001043.1	Wk3-1	Alpha box	MAT1-1	JABCQQ010000190 .1
GX01	HMG	MAT1-2	JMJT01003081.1	Y34	HMG	MAT1-2	AHZS01001895.1
H08-1a	Alpha box	MAT1-1	NKQF01001216.1	Y93-164a-1	HMG	MAT1-2	AB080673.2
H08-1c	Alpha box	MAT1-1	NKQG01001098.1	Y93-164g-1	Alpha box	MAT1-1	AB080672.2
HB-14	HMG	MAT1-2	MQPH01000899.1	YN07205e	Alpha box	MAT1-1	MQQS01000041.1
HB-LTH18	HMG	MAT1-2	MQPI01000386.1	YN072310	HMG	MAT1-2	MQQT01000101.1
HB1	Alpha box	MAT1-1	MF993977.1	YN072311	HMG	MAT1-2	MQQU01001169.1
HB12	HMG	MAT1-2	JMJS01001883.1	YN072313	HMG	MAT1-2	MQQV01001097.1
HN-0812-3	HMG	MAT1-2	MQPJ01001196.1	YN08181e	HMG	MAT1-2	MQQW01000137.1
HN-158	Alpha box	MAT1-1	MQPK01000930.1	YN08182c	Alpha box	MAT1-1	MQQX01001783.1
HN06	HMG	MAT1-2	JMJR01007313.1	YN126311	HMG	MAT1-2	MQQY01001931.1
HN10-1604	Alpha box	MAT1-1	MQPL01000533.1	YN126441	HMG	MAT1-2	MQQZ01001547.1
HO	Alpha box	MAT1-1	PJYL01000001.1	YN8773-19	Alpha box	MAT1-1	MQRA01000453.1
Hoku-1	Alpha box	MAT1-1	AB080668.2	YN8773R-27	HMG	MAT1-2	MQRB01000821.1
IA1	HMG	MAT1-2	PJYK01000173.1	ZJ00-10	HMG	MAT1-2	MQRC01000266.1
IB33	Alpha box	MAT1-1	PJYJ01000102.1	ZJ08-41	HMG	MAT1-2	MQRD01001810.1
IB49	Alpha box	MAT1-1	PJYI01000147.1	ZJ15	HMG	MAT1-2	JMJM01001950.1
IC17	Alpha box	MAT1-1	PJYH01000101.1	ZJ2011-7-1	HMG	MAT1-2	MQRE01000469.1